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Research Article

**NURSES MANAGERES' ATTRIBUTES TO PROMOTE
CHANGE IN WARDS**¹Asif Raza Gill, ²Ms. Sana Sehar, ³Muhammad Afzal, ⁴Dr. Syed Amir Gilani.¹Student. The University of Lahore, ²Assistant professor, The University of Lahore, ³associate professor. The University of Lahore, ⁴Dean faculty of allied health sciences. The University of Lahore.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Sidra, a staff nurse who has been training for four years, has begun working on a new, evening shift, medical-surgical department. During the changing of shift, she sees other nurses giving minimal report and believes they are in a rush to get back. Sidra also pointed out that 3 p.m. timed medications are not recorded as administered. Three to four days a week, she had to contact nurses at home to make sure the prescriptions are provided. For her calls, the nurses are often very annoyed. As sidra addresses the topic of all cases with her head nurse, he says that this has always been a concern and he congratulated her and he promises that he will intervene as soon as possible. Organizational behavior analysis would give full understanding of people's behaviors and attitudes within a company with a systematic strategy for a new manager. Motivation is important because an unmotivated workplace contributes to decreased commitment and therefore efficiency, while a motivated workforce is good for everyone.

Corresponding author:**Asif Raza Gill,**
Student, The University of Lahore.

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INTRODUCTION:**SITUATION:**

Sidra, a staff nurse who has been training for four years, has begun working on a new, evening shift, medical-surgical department. During the changing of shift, she sees other nurses giving minimal report and believes they are in a rush to get back. Sidra also pointed out that 3 p.m. timed medications are not recorded as administered. Three to four days a week, she had to contact nurses at home to make sure the prescriptions are provided. For her calls, the nurses are often very annoyed. As sidra addresses the topic of all cases with her head nurse, he says that this has always been a concern and he congratulated her and he promises that he will intervene as soon as possible. After few days he has a few other ideas that may make it easier for the nurses to remember to chart medications and report off to the evening nurses with more thorough information. He presents a new flow chart reporting sheet based on SBAR, the communication tool using Situation, Background, Assessment, and Recommendation, to all staff nurses. He identified achievement, affiliation, and develops suitable motivational strategies to meet needed requirements and used some strategies to promote good behavior in his staff members.

PROBLEM SOLVING STRATEGIES WHICH HE ADAPTED TO RESOLVE PROBLEM:

He has used positive feedback to motivate individual employees, He has created unit priorities that address institutional and subordinate desires, He has maintained a unit culture which reduces job-dissatisfied employees. He encouraged a group culture based on workplace motivators (created a pressure necessary to maintain productivity) He clearly communicated aspirations to subordinates, He demonstrated and conveyed sincere appreciation, interest, loyalty and sense of belonging to subordinates. To raise a sense of achievement in colleagues, he delegated work duties commensurate with worker skills and past performance.

MANAGEMENT PROCESS:**Creating motivating climate:**

Since the organization has such an effect on internal motivation, it's important to look at organizational environments and behaviors that directly affect employee motivation. Such as companies also explicitly and covertly promote the identity of each worker and his or her performance within the organization.

Furthermore, many organizations mistakenly believe that if a modest reward results in desirable behavior, a larger incentive would result in the desired behavior

even more. Therefore, the morale of an employee must rise in proportion to the benefit or bonus level. It's just not true. There seems to be assumed limit above which there is no extra value or weight to improve the reward performance. Organizations therefore need to establish compensation programs that are reliably compatible with workplace beliefs.

Managers should always be mindful of the personal beliefs of an individual and try to pay the worker accordingly. A leadership capability is the ability to recognize that person as a unique individual who is empowered differently and then respond on those discrepancies.

Strategies for making a motivating environment:

The manager can do a lot of things to build a motivational atmosphere. Sometimes it is as basic as creating a positive and motivating atmosphere to promote the morale of a subordinate. The policy value is only the time and energy of the manager. Nonetheless, some managers say that appreciation, rewards, development opportunities and clear goals are also important to developing positive work environments such as having clear expectations of employees and successfully expressing those expectations. Be fair and consistent in working with all staff, be a firm decision maker using a fitting form of decision-making.

- Develop the teamwork concept, build community plans and activities and create a team spirit.
- Integrate the wishes of workers and want with the goals and intent of the company.
- Remove conventional workers blocks from the work to be done.
- Create stimulating environments and provide opportunities for growth.
- Give recognition and praise to superiors whenever possible.
- Make sure to understand the reason behind behavior of workers.
- Reward good behavior; be vigilant in coping with unwanted behavior.
- Let workers exercise as much as possible personal discretion.
- Develop a trustful friendship with staff and support them.
- Let workers have as much power of their workplace environment as possible.

MANAGEMENT PROCESS:**Motivation Theory**

- McClelland's Learned Needs

McClelland Theory:

Motives direct an individual to action according to this theory suggesting that individuals are motivated via three basic needs such as success, affiliation and energy. Achievement oriented people are actively focused on improving what is, they turn ideas into practice, sensibly and responsibly. On the other hand, concerned with affiliation, people center their attention at families and friends, their over-productivity is less so as they perceive their contribution to society differently from those focused to accomplishment.

Another research indicates that women typically have higher needs for association than men, and that nurses usually have high needs for affiliation, power

oriented individuals are driven by the strength that can be obtained by specific action (Ashkenazi, 2017)

McClelland theorizes that managers should define their workers' requirements for accomplishment, allegiance, and strength, and build effective motivational methods to meet those needs.

Research shows that motivation is extremely complex and that there is a considerable difference in what motivates different individuals. Managers therefore need to consider what can be done at unit level to create environment that helps the employee to expand, improve morale and efficiency, and remove discontent that consumes resources and fosters resentment

(Morsiani, G., Bagnasco, A., & Sasso, L. 2017).

Critical role for motivation:

It is important for managers to consider why and how workers are motivated to take full advantage of a worker's ability to learn and succeed when they handle a Diverse Workforce. Critical role in encouragement. To encourage staff to learn and work at their best is a complex and difficult task for a manager. No two men, i.e. no two workers are alike, including the two who do the same job. Two different

(McClelland Theory)

people will have two distinct needs and desires at all times. In fact, what motivates a worker to do better today may not inspire him in the next year, or next week, or even next hour. A driven group of workers, though, is a huge hope. If workers are inspired by success, education and happiness, they can dramatically improve from which all profits, including the company (Cherry, 2016).

DISCUSSION:

Cause and effects:

One of the most effective, but often ignored and underused, motivators that the director can use to build a motivational environment is positive reinforcement, validating the worker's effort. Negative feedback makes workers feel like they're being criticized for trying, and if there's constant negative feedback the employee will give up trying (Smith, C. M., 2018).

If rewards lack integrity, there is an increased risk that the incentive itself will become a source of rivalry and thus lower morals. The mentality prevails that "a limited number of awards are open and someone else's award reduces the chances of getting one of them; thus, "I cannot accept recognition of my peers.". Furthermore, praising the actions of one person and not the behavior of another who has done a similar task at a similar level encourages envy and can demotivate (Kodama, , H. 2017).

To order to use positive reinforcement and incentive as motivating tools, incentives must be a genuine achievement and must be quite individual to nature. For example, as an incentive that motivates workers, most managers incorrectly consider annual merit pay increases (Kodama, , H. 2017).

While managers must foster excellence within achievable goals, there is also a need for support of people who make genuine attempts to do things better even if they have not accomplished excellence (Heinen, M. 2019).

FUTURE PLAN:

As a manager I will developed this plan in future if I will in that situation, include:

Plan and set goals, it's a great way to motivate employees:

That's where SMART goals come into play. They're bite-sized goals that appear easier to achieve, with each one bringing your team one step closer to completing the big goal.

SMART stands for:

Specific, Measurable, Agreed Upon, Realistic and Time-based or Trackable.

Reward and incentivize:

Not all work provides employees with an immediate reward, but providing incentives helps them identify targets: nothing works better than a reward to inspire employees to achieve their goals.

Remember that trust breeds loyalty:

Showing confidence and trust in staff skills would help them feel part of the team and encourage greater morale to my organization It's natural for them to be more inspired when workers become engaged.

Furthermore I will provide recognition for hard work, will promote a sense of unity, tolerance and acceptance, will improve management of multicultural groups, will reduce of conflict among multicultural team members and will improve communication across the organization improved productivity.

CONCLUSION:

Organizational behavior analysis would give full understanding of people's behaviors and attitudes

within a company with a systematic strategy for a new manager. Motivation is important because an unmotivated workplace contributes to decreased

commitment and therefore efficiency, while a motivated workforce is good for everyone.

McClelland's Human Motivation Theory

Identified three motivators

All three are present in each person, but one motivator will dominate

People will have different characteristics depending on their dominant motivator

REFERENCES:

1. Smith, C. M., & Johnson, C. S. (2018). Preparing nurse leaders in nursing professional development: Theories applied to leadership in nursing professional development. *Journal for nurses in professional development*, 34(1), 38-40.
2. Ashkenazi, L., Livshiz-Riven, I., Romem, P., & Grinstein-Cohen, O. (2017). Male nurses in Israel: Barriers, motivation, and how they are perceived by nursing students. *Journal of Professional Nursing*, 33(2), 162-169.
3. Kodama, Y., & Fukahori, H. (2017). Nurse managers' attributes to promote change in their wards: A qualitative study. *Nursing open*, 4(4), 209-217.
4. Gustafsson, L. K., & Stenberg, M. (2017). Crucial contextual attributes of nursing leadership towards a care ethics. *Nursing ethics*, 24(4), 419-429.
5. Morsiani, G., Bagnasco, A., & Sasso, L. (2017). How staff nurses perceive the impact of nurse managers' leadership style in terms of job satisfaction: a mixed method study. *Journal of nursing management*, 25(2), 119-128.
6. Heinen, M., Van Oostveen, C., Peters, J., Vermeulen, H., & Huis, A. (2019). An integrative review of Leadership Competencies and Attributes in Advanced Nursing Practice. *Journal of advanced nursing*.
7. Cherry, B., & Jacob, S. R. (2016). *Contemporary nursing: Issues, trends, & management*. Elsevier Health Sciences.